

**DENSIFIED CELLULOSE MATERIALS AND DELIGNIFIED WOOD
REINFORCED COMPOSITES**

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ABSTRACT

The development of sustainable materials from renewable resources is one of the key challenges in today's materials science. Wood has great potential to play an important role in future materials advancement due to its excellent mechanical properties and high abundance. In this regard, two novel concepts for the development of high-performance wood-based materials in scalable top-down approaches are presented. Both concepts, Densified Cellulose Materials (DCMs) and Delignified Wood Reinforced Polymers (DWRPs), are based on delignification and densification of wood. Matrix free DCMs possess good tensile properties with a stiffness up to 40 GPa and strength up to 250 MPa. The high mechanical properties are obtained by a combination of high fibre volume content (FVC) of up to 80% and stress transfer throughout the cellulose scaffold enabled by mechanically interlocked fibre-fibre interfaces. Matrix infiltrated DWRPs reveal excellent tensile properties with elastic moduli of up to 70 GPa and 600 MPa strength. The epoxy matrix is vacuum infiltrated into the scaffold before densification and curing and provides an additional stiffening effect. The low intrinsic density of cellulose fibres results in attractive specific tensile properties, which are above previously reported values obtained for natural fibre composites such as flax or sisal. By scalable open-mold vacuum processing, DCMs with high tensile properties can be fabricated to partially replace less sustainable materials such as glass fibre reinforced composites in the future.

1 INTRODUCTION

Wood combines low density with good mechanical properties due to its hierarchical structure across several length scales. On cell wall level, stiff reinforcing cellulose fibrils are embedded in a compliant matrix of lignin and hemicelluloses. On macroscopic level, wood cells (mainly tracheids in softwood) are hollow tubes, which are unidirectionally aligned and provide the mechanical stability to the tree. Cells are embedded in a matrix of lignin and pectin and are connected through bordered pits to provide continuous flow channels for water transportation in a tree. These flow channels have been used for wood functionalization to add new properties, such as magnetism [1], improved flame retardancy [2] or stimuli responsiveness [3]. Infiltration of polymers into wood led to enhanced weathering resistance [4] and mechanical performance [5].

Recently, the interest in the fabrication of wood based cellulose scaffolds via structural retaining partial or complete delignification has been increasing. Cellulose scaffolds have been used for the production of transparent wood [6], oil absorbents [7], filters [8], and for structural wood based materials [9-11]. Delignification results in lignin removal in between neighbouring cells, in the cell corner and

middle lamella region, and in the cell wall. Upon drying, the material shrinks and leads to the formation of mechanical interlocks at the fibre-fibre interface. This results in stable cellulosic scaffolds, which can further be used as reinforcing element [10].

In the following, new wood-based materials based on structural retained delignified wood are presented. The main concepts of matrix-free Densified Cellulose Materials (DCMs) and matrix containing Delignified Wood Reinforced Polymers (DWRPs) are explained and tensile properties of both are discussed. Additionally, a scalable manufacturing process for DCMs, the open-mold vacuum processing, is presented.

2 DENSIFIED CELLULOSE MATERIAL (DCM)

DCMs are produced in a simple two-step process. Native wood is first delignified by a structural retaining acidic approach. This results in a lightweight cellulose scaffold, which is further densified after conditioning at 95% RH at 20 °C (Fig. 1). The final fibre volume content can be adjusted by controlling the densification degree [9]. DCMs are processed out of bulk wood- (we used the dimensions 100 x 20 x 10 mm³) or from thin wood samples (e.g. veneers, thickness 1.5 mm), which are stacked on top of each other before densification to obtain thicker samples.

Figure 1: Illustration of the manufacturing process of Densified Cellulose Materials (DCMs). Native wood is delignified in a first step. The obtained cellulose scaffold is densified in a second step [9].

2.1 Mechanical properties and mechanical gradients

Through densification, FVCs can be controlled and high values of up to 80% are reached due to cellulose fibers deformability. This corresponds to an elastic modulus of up to 40 GPa and strength of approximately 250 MPa. The elastic modulus increases linearly with FVC up to 60%. Interestingly, between 60 and 80% FVC, we observe a distinct deviation from the linear behavior towards higher values (Fig. 2b), which could be explained by increased interactions between neighboring fibers through enhanced mechanical interlocking and hydrogen bonding. Above 80% FVC, stiffness values decrease, due to challenges in processing of high-density samples. Cellulose fibers start to flow under the applied pressure and results in fiber misalignment and cracks [10].

Densification can either be conducted throughout the whole sample, to homogeneously increase the mechanical properties or local densification and topographic laminate stacking followed by densification can be used to obtain mechanical gradients within one sample (Fig. 2a). This can be used to reduce stress concentrations in a part.

Figure 2: (a) Local densification and topographic stacking followed by densification both lead to mechanical gradients within a sample. (b) Tensile elastic moduli of DCMs with FVCs between 20 and 80% [10].

2.2 Formability

Delignified wood is shapeable in its wet state owing to the free water in between neighboring cells. This water-filled gaps allow neighboring cells to slide past along each other, which enables a shear deformation of the sample. Hence, the cellulose scaffold can be shaped to optimize the fiber alignment for external loading-conditions in the final part as demonstrated in Fig. 3 [10]. Here, we utilize this concept to produce an open-hole reinforcement. First, we tune the fiber flow by simply shaping the delignified veneer (Fig. 3c). Second, we add additional layers of delignified veneer on top of the highly loaded regions to create a density gradient (Fig. 3d) [10]. It is important to note, that prior densification the material needs to be conditioned at a maximum relative humidity of 95% in order to avoid counter pressure from the saturated sample, which leads to fiber rupture and fiber misalignment.

Figure 3: (a) Shaped bulk wood sample [9], (b) delignified veneer, (c) shaped delignified veneer and (d) shaped delignified veneer with a reinforcing layer added by topographic stacking [10].

2.3 Open-mold vacuum processing

The newly developed open-mold vacuum process allows the manufacturing of shaped DCMs in an efficient and scalable manner. Shaping, densification and drying are conducted simultaneously, which comes with the advantage that complex shapes can be combined with high densification. For manufacturing, wet delignified wood veneers are draped on top of a porous (e.g. 3D printed) mold (Fig. 4). Handling of delignified wood is challenging, as the cellulose scaffold is rather fragile in wet state. Therefore, metal meshes, which are already placed in between veneers during delignification, are used for transfer and drape of the cellulose material. A textile layer can optionally be added between the cellulose scaffold and the mold for a smooth surface finish. A second textile layer is placed on top of the wet delignified wood, and the whole setup is sealed with a vacuum bag. Vacuum is applied to densify and dry the cellulose material, while water escapes through the porous mold and through the vacuum bag bleeder and is collected in a cool-trap (Fig. 5). Alternatively to porous molds, a porous layer can be

placed between cellulose material and vacuum bag to enable drying. After drying, the densified material is demolded and the setup can be reused for the next part.

Figure 4: (a) Shapeable delignified wood veneer in wet state, (b) draping of delignified wood to a 3D printed mold by using a metal grid as support, (c) 1 layer of delignified wood draped on mold.

Figure 5: Illustration of the open-mold vacuum process. (a) Porous mold, (b) textile and delignified wood draped on top of the porous mold, (c) textile and vacuum bag are placed on top of the cellulose material and vacuum is applied, (d) demolding of final sample.

2.4 Manufacturing of composite parts

To manufacture composite parts, multiple layers of veneers are stacked on top of each other in a defined layup (e.g. unidirectional, $[0, 90]$). To improve bonding between individual layers and decrease the risk of delamination, a water-based adhesive starch (16.5 wt% starch in water) was used to produce a 8-layer cellulose-starch layup (8 x 1.5 mm veneer) with a final thickness of 2.5 mm using an applied vacuum in the range of 10^{-2} bar. The final sample thickness corresponds to a densification of approximately $\frac{1}{4}$ of the initial thickness of dry delignified wood and results in elastic moduli values in the range of 20 GPa and strength values in the range of 200 MPa [10]. Because the cellulose-starch composite is entirely bio based, it can also disintegrate in water, which is advantageous when it comes to recycling or disposal at the end of life. However, this comes with the disadvantage of a reduction in mechanical properties in humid conditions and proper hydrophobic coatings as we have shown in Frey et al. 2019 [10] need to be applied.

Figure 6: Shows structures of (a) a car door panel and (b) a tachometer cover manufactured by the open-mold vacuum processing as proof of principle.

3 DELIGNIFIED WOOD REINFORCED POLYMER (DWRP)

Matrix-free DCMs already show relatively high tensile properties. These values can further be increased by the infiltration of a thermosetting polymer followed by densification and crosslinking. Here we present DWRPs that are manufactured by the infiltration of an epoxy system with very low viscosity and long pot life (RIM 235/RIMH238, Hexion). The infiltration is conducted on delignified, oven dried bulk wood samples (100 x 20 x 10 mm³). A standard VARI infiltration in longitudinal direction is used for the epoxy infiltration. The epoxy flows through pits, which are natural connections used for water transportation in the tree. After complete infiltration and before epoxy curing, the infiltrated sample is densified in a closed mold (CRTM mold), and results in fully infiltrated DWRPs. The FVC can again be adjusted by the densification degree.

Figure 7: Illustration of Delignified Wood Reinforced Polymer (DWRP) manufacturing process. Native wood is delignified, the cellulose scaffold is infiltrated with a polymer and the composite is densified followed by curing of the matrix.

3.1 Mechanical properties

Tensile tests were conducted on samples with FVCs of approximately 25%, 50% and 70%. Samples with FVCs up to 50% were compared to reference materials, including wood, delignified wood (DW) and glass fibre reinforced polymer (GFRP) composites. FVCs of 70% were not obtained for GFRP due to the incompressibility of glass fibres and DW due to shape recovery after densification of dried cellulose scaffolds. Tensile stiffness and tensile strength of DWRP increased with the FVC. However, the increase in stiffness exceeds traditional composite models such as the Halpin-Tsai model as shown in Fig. 8b assuming a delignified wood fibre elastic modulus of 50 GPa and an aspect ratio of 100. Our values even exceed the upper limit of the rule of mixtures (ROM). This trend is similar for matrix-free composites as shown in the DCMs part (2.1), and underlines the strong fibre-fibre interactions that are even enhanced for high FVCs. Strong fibre-fibre interactions in combination with high FVCs and with the matrix stiffening effect provided by the matrix in lumen and pits result in high tensile stiffness up to 70 GPa and strength of about 600 MPa. Additionally, the low density of cellulose fibres results in very high specific tensile properties, which outperform matrix-free delignified wood and GFRPs. In comparison to previously reported natural fibre reinforced composites such as flax [12,13], sisal [14] and wood based composites [5,11,16], high FVC DWRP is among the best performing composites as shown in Fig. 9.

Figure 8: Tensile properties of DWRP in comparison to wood, delignified wood (DW) and glass fiber reinforced polymer (GFRP) composites. (a) Tensile modulus and (b) comparison of DWRP moduli to rule of mixture (ROM) and Halpin-Tsai model for an assumed modulus of elasticity of 50 GPa and an aspect ratio of 100 for delignified wood fibers. (c) Tensile strength and (d) specific tensile modulus versus specific tensile strength.

Figure 9: Specific tensile/bending modulus versus specific tensile/bending strength for DWRPs compared to references from literature.

4 CONCLUSIONS

We have developed matrix-free as well as polymer infiltrated wood-based high-performance materials. Matrix-free DCMs demonstrate tensile properties of up to 40 GPa stiffness and 250 MPa in strength. These high tensile properties of the cellulose material are a result of strong fiber-fiber interfaces that seem to enable stress transfer within the cellulose scaffold in dry state. In wet state, however, these fiber-fiber interfaces tend to behave weaker because the presence of water in between neighboring cells allows for shear-formability of the cellulose scaffold. This deformability can be used in an advantageous manner to adjust the fiber flow within the cellulose material in order to optimize for external loading conditions. Additionally, mechanical gradients can be created by local densification or topographic stacking, which further help to reduce stress concentration. Polymer infiltration into the cellulose scaffold before densification followed by curing of the matrix results in DWRPs. Compared to DCMs, the reinforcing scaffold is stiffened by the matrix, resulting in a stiffness up to 70 GPa and strength of 600 MPa at a FVC of 80%. DCMs and DWRPs both present new approaches to produce high-performance sustainable materials. The open-mold vacuum processing of DCMs is scalable and is especially promising for more sustainable and recyclable composite parts, replacing for example glass fiber composites in the future.

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